

CAREER MATURITY TRAINING TOWARDS CAREER ORIENTATION OF CLASS XII STUDENTS IN SMA 10 BOGOR, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

Adolescence, through their development years, has tasks to be completed. One of the developmental tasks is to choose and prepare for their career in the future. Mastering all the necessary skills is important to decide for the right career. However, according to a survey involving students of class XII of SMA Negeri 10 Bogor (10 Senior High School Bogor), 50% of the participants have not yet decided what they are going to be in the future. This study showed that these students have not yet engaged in career maturity to plan for their career. Based on this study, the researchers planned to design a career maturity training to enhance their skills on deciding for the right career. The purpose of the research is to discover the effectively of career maturity training on grade XII high school students. This research uses *quasi-experimental* approach, with *Single Group Pre-test-Post-test* research design and involves and involves 21 students with low-to-medium career maturity level. Before the pre-test result was handed over, the training score of all students were 57. After the training was finished, the post-test result was 154. Based on this data analysis results, we can conclude that there is a significant result difference between the before and after the researchers gave the training to grade XII students. It means that the training given is considered effective.

Keywords: career maturity, adolescence, training

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1. Introduction

Adolescence is a transition period from childhood into adulthood. During the transition period, adolescents are required to fulfil development tasks related to attitudes, knowledge, and skills (deeds and behaviours) that should be possessed by a teenager in accordance with the development phase. According to Havighurst (Syamsu Yusuf, 2004: 83) in adolescence there are several developmental tasks that must be completed, one of the developmental tasks that must be achieved by adolescents is to choose and prepare to plan a career in the future. Mastery of career skills is very much needed considering that teenagers have thought about how they can fulfil their desired needs in their lives. This is in line with the opinion of Hurlock (2002: 221) that adolescents begin to think about their future seriously. Teenagers learn to distinguish between career choices that are preferred and aspired.

High School (SMA) students include individuals who enter middle adolescence aged 15-18 years. In *Super's life stages and sub stages on the typical development tasks* states that ideally at the age of 14-18 years, a person should have been in the *crystallizing* stage, where he already knows his interests and capacities and has his career choices. However, the phenomenon that occurs in the field is not the case. Some of the teenagers do not even have the curiosity of their careers, some of them still have many desires for a career and some are not able to assess their interests and abilities. Meanwhile, they must continue their education to a further level or work. As a result, some teenagers just continue their education but do not refer to career choices, there are also teenagers who after graduation feel confused and do not know what they want to continue their education with and where. This phenomenon is still quite common in various educational institutions in Indonesia.

As research conducted by Triana (Setyawati, 2005) which shows that 45% of high school students participating in the research do not yet have a career plan to choose next because they are still in doubt. This is supported again by research conducted by Saifuddin, et al. (2017) of high school students in Surakarta which shows that 30.71% of students participating in the research do not have a clear picture of the future. A similar phenomenon is also experienced by students of SMAN 10 Bogor. Based on a survey conducted by 50% of class XII students in the high school do not yet have strong sufficient knowledge in career planning. This can be seen from the description of the survey results as follows: 1) there are still many students who are confused in choosing the field of study because they do not know what to choose and on what basis, 2) there are still many students who are hesitant to choose between work and school, 3) still many students are still lacking confidence to choose the field of study and the field of work to be chosen, 4) many students who have not yet explored their abilities or job requirements to help them decide for a field of study or field of work, 5) there are still many students who do not do a clear planning to choose their career field, and 6) there are still many students who do not yet know the importance of adjusting their abilities to work requirements. In addition to the initial survey conducted on these students, information gathering was also

conducted on Career Guidance teachers at SMAN 10 Bogor. Based on the interview, it was found that, according to the teacher, students spent more time searching for requirements on how to get into college, rather than taking into account the suitability between their abilities and the requirements they had to fulfil to enter college and many students were still confused about what they would become (whether continuing studies or working or getting married).

The search results have given a picture that some students of class XII at SMAN 10 Bogor do not have career maturity. These students do not yet have a career image or further education to be involved in and do not yet know the strategies or steps in achieving the desired career field. Based on the career development task by Super (in Sharf, 2006), a teenager who is 17 years old should have been in the *crystallizing* stage, where he already knows his interests and capacities and has his career choices. Next, they are expected to make concrete plans towards fulfilling their career goals.

In the concept of career maturity theory by Super (in Sharf, 2006), individuals who are ready with their career choices will have 5 conditions which are indicators of one's career maturity, namely: (1) Start thinking about their choice of working field; (2) Have planning and information about work fields of interest; (3) Have a consistent or stable choice of work of interest; (4) Realize self's potential; (5) Having a career choice with comprehensive consideration regarding self potential and information about the field of work to be chosen. According to Super (in Sharf, 2006), individual readiness in facing career choices as stated above can be identified through the way an individual plans his career (*career planning*), how to explore their career (*career exploration*), how to make their decision on a career (*decision making*), and complete information about the world of work (*knowledge of work information*). This means that intervention efforts made to increase the readiness of individuals in facing their career choices depend on the dimensions that become individual barriers.

Based on these problems, the researchers designed an intervention program to help class XII students to have readiness in facing their career choices. The form of intervention chosen by the researchers is a training program developed on the theory of career development by Super as learning materials, which aims to improve the readiness of students to face career options.

2. Materials & Methods

2.1 Research subject

The subject of research is 21 students of grade XII, male and female students aged 17 years old, who plan on continuing to college or work, and the subject has a desire to develop readiness to choose for their career.

2.2 Material

A person's career maturity is formed based on several models of career development. One model to describe a career maturity development is *The Archway Career Determinant*

theory. The theory emphasizes the importance of biographical and geographical concepts that will help generate feelings of self (*self*) and feelings of planning (*playfulness*). According to Super, career maturity is defined as readiness to overcome or complete developmental tasks in accordance with one's developmental stage (in Savickas, 2004). Meanwhile, according to Crites, career maturity is a match between real individual career behaviour with expected career behaviour at a certain age at each stage of development (in Savickas, 2004).

In general, the process of career maturity occurs during the career exploration stage, or in adolescence until early adulthood (Super in Brown & Lent, 2005). According to Super (in Sharf, 2006), at the transition stage from early development stage to exploration stage or at adolescence stage, an individual will also be at career development stage, so adequate career orientation is important to have, namely the readiness of individuals to make the right career decisions. According to Crites, individual readiness to make career decisions can be understood through several concepts that shape career maturity. Career maturity itself has two dimensions; they are attitude dimension and cognitive dimension (in Brown & Lent, 2005). The attitude dimension is the attitudes and feelings of individuals related to effective career decision making. The cognitive dimension is an individual's awareness of the need to make career decisions and to understand the career of his choice. This cognitive competence is needed to make good career decisions, including adequate knowledge about higher education and the world of work plus individual skills and abilities needed in the field. This cognitive dimension is important to measure because it will direct the individual to action (Savickas, 2004).

2.3 Components of Super Career Maturity

Super stated (in Sharf 2006) there are 4 aspects of career maturity, namely 1) *career planning*, 2) *career exploration*, 3) *decision making*, and 4) *world of work information*, and 5) *knowledge of the preferred occupational group*. **Career Planning**; Career planning is a process carried out by someone in an effort to achieve their career goals. Career plan measures how far or how much a person's thoughts are directed to planning his career. **Career Exploration**; The desire to explore or find information is a basic concept of career exploration. Students are willing to use existing sub-resources such as parents, acquaintances, friends, teachers, counsellors, books, films and so forth. *Career exploration* is different from *career planning*, while career exploration focuses on thinking and planning about the future, career planning is formed by the resources surrounded the self. **Decision Making**; A perception that believes students must know that making career decisions is important in the concept of vocational maturity, as conceptualized by Super. This concept emphasizes in the ability to use knowledge and thought to make career decisions. **World of Work Information**; The concept of *world of work information* has two basic components. First, is the acknowledgment of the importance of developmental tasks, such as student's acknowledgment to explore their interests and abilities, how students learn about their work, and reasons why people can switch jobs. Second, have a

thorough knowledge of job assignments in a variety of job choices, as well as a behaviour expected of job applicants.

2.4 Realism

Realism is a part of the career maturity concept by Super (in Sharf, 2006). Super describes realism as "*a combination of cognition and affection by combining personality, personal reports, and objective data that compares attitudes (achievements and abilities) of individuals with attitudes (achievements and abilities) needed in a career*". Therefore, to find out whether one's career choices are realistic or not, students need to know their own attitudes and know the attitudes needed by the majors in a college of choice, then compare them to make the right career decision.

2.5 Teenagers and Career Maturity Super

Teenagers in the concept of life stages and sub stages based on the types of development tasks by Super are in the age range of 14-18 years with the task of crystallization development. The crystallization stage is the stage where someone clearly knows what they want to do. They learn about the job levels that will be suitable for them, and they learn what skills are needed in jobs that are of interest to them. Many high school students go through this stage. At this stage, they begin to realize the abilities, interests, and values. Work experience and work knowledge help one to narrow down one's choices. Based on the explanation of the theories mentioned above, it can be concluded that knowledge about self-understanding and career orientation process is needed as a guide for teens to plan careers and make career decisions.

2.6 Training Method

Training, as defined by Sahlan (2011), is a learning and teaching process that uses systematic and organized procedures so that the individuals who participate in the training get an understanding of technical knowledge and or skills for specific purposes. In this research there are several methods used, namely lectures, modified lectures, *task exercises*, group discussions, case studies, and *role playing*.

3. Method

This study uses the approach of *quasi-experimental*, with *Single Group Pre test – Post test Design (Before-After)* (Graziano & Raulin, 2000). *This Pre test – Post test design* was chosen in consideration of the purpose of this study, to see if there are changes that occur in the research subjects caused by the intervention in the form of training in readiness in facing career choices. For this purpose, it is necessary to take the initial condition of readiness of the subjects in facing career choices obtained through *pre test* and information about subject's conditions after getting the intervention of readiness in facing career choices training, obtained through the *post test*.

Table 1: Design one-group pretest-posttest study

Pretest	Treatment	Posttest
O_1	X	O_2

In this training the researchers used training instruments in the form of *paper-and-pencil tests* to collect data about the learning outcomes that existed in the participants before and after the training (*pre-test and post-test*). The researcher made 10 questions about the material in the training. The test consists of 10 essay questions. One question answered correctly is given a score of 1 and if answering 10 questions correctly will get a total score of 10. Questions given are based on the provided training material, this aims to find out whether participants are informed about the process of making career decisions prior to the training and how each-participant's mastering of the training material after the training is given. The questions for the pre-test and post-test contain same questions. All the instruments above are only used for training-purposes and conducted at SMA Negeri 10 in Bogor.

The results of the research data were processed using the statistical method Wilcoxon-Test (signed rank test) with the ratio data type. This type of calculation is used to find out the-result difference of the participants before and after the training is given. Wilcoxon test is the development of *The Sign Test*. The comparison of the accuracy between Wilcoxon and The-Sign Test is that, not only does it show the direction differentiation; it also shows the group or-given treatment difference.

4. Results and Analysis

4.1 Results

The effectiveness of this training is seen from the effectiveness of *learning* as measured from the *pre-test-treatment-post-test* method. That is, the *pre-test* is carried out before the training and *post-test* is carried out after the training is given to the subject. The purpose of *learning* measurement is to find out whether the training given to participants really has an effect or impact on increasing knowledge and insight about the career orientation process. The hypothesis of this training evaluation is that there are differences in the results between the pre-test and post-test scores after the training is given. In this measurement, researchers used a data collection tool in the form of questions totalling 10 questions. Then the data is tabulated and calculated using SPSS 25. The following data is the results of the pre-test and post-test:

Table 2: Data of pre test – post test

Subject	Score	
	Pre	Post
1	3	9
2	2	7
3	4	9
4	1	9
5	1	6
6	3	8
7	2	7
8	1	2
9	1	3
10	3	9
11	1	8
12	3	8
13	1	7
14	3	9
15	4	8
16	4	8
17	5	9
18	6	9
19	4	8
20	1	2
21	4	9
Total	57	154

The calculation results are as follows:

Table 3: Pre-test and Post-test Results

	Post test - Pre test
Z	-4.038 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Basis for making the Wilcoxon Test:

1. If the Asymp Sig value <0.05, the hypothesis is accepted.
2. If the Asymp Sig value > 0.05, then the hypothesis is rejected.

In the table above shows that the results Asymp Sig (2-tailed) 0:00 <0:05, which if the probability of test results is of <0.05, indicate that Ho is accepted. Therefore, it can be concluded that there are significant differences in results before and after the career orientation training process is given to students of class XII Social Science 3. This means that the training provided is effective.

4.2 Analysis

Based on the theory used, the researcher designed a career maturity training in class XII students with modules that have been adjusted from the results of needs analysis with the theory used. As explained above that in order to plan careers and make career

decisions, students must have knowledge about themselves and information about the career orientation process which includes knowledge about *career planning*, *career exploration*, *decision making*, *world of work information*, and *decision making*.

4.3 Self-knowledge

Self-knowledge is one aspect that students must possess and understand to plan their career after graduating from high school. Based on the results of the questionnaire given 75% of students do not know about themselves thoroughly. This is supported again by the results of pre-test scoring on "*self-understanding*" aspects with scores below the average. This became one of the training materials in the first session. The researcher designed the training with the theme "*know yourself*" through "*self evaluating*" in the form of *paper-and-pencil* test. Researchers gave *Workbooks* containing 21 statements of lattice aspects of *self*. The results of measurements of "*self-understanding*" aspect are seen from the questions *pre-test-post-test* at no. 1 and 2. The score result of pre-test number 2 and 3 are still below the average of 50%. Whereas after being given training, the results of student scores increase above 50%.

4.4 Career Planning

Conceptual definition of *career planning* is a process carried out by someone in an effort to achieve his career goals. The operational definition of *career planning* in this training is student's devotion to the activities of career information seeking as well as the level of knowledge possessed by individuals about aspects of the campus and the department they want. Career planning measures how far or how much a person's thoughts are directed to planning his career. Some examples of activities that someone wants to do in career planning are: learning about job information, talking to other people or older people about the career plans, taking courses that can help to decide on a career, following extracurricular activities or working part time, and joining various job trainings. The most important thing from the concept of career planning is the amount of planning that has been done by individuals. To find out someone's *career planning*, we must know not only what activities being carried out by individuals, but also their thoughts about what they have done. Discussing about their future plans, including courses or training to be taken by someone, choice of college and faculty, or planning the first or second choice for the desired course. Before given training on *career planning*, there were still many students who were confused about what to do and how to do career planning after graduating from high school. This data was gained from interviews, needs analysis, and the results of pre-test measurements on aspects of *career planning*. Based on the needs analysis, 19 students are at low category and the pre-test score below 50%. After being given career maturity training on *career planning* aspect, students begin to know and understand one aspect of *career planning* for planning and making right career decisions. The results of the pre-test score on this aspect are in questions number 3 and 4 are at 50%.

4.5 Career Exploration

The conceptual definition of career exploration is the desire of students to use existing resources such as parents, acquaintances, friends, teachers, counsellors, books, films and so on. While the operational definition in this study is the desire of individuals to explore various types of campuses and majors from various information sources and have the initiative to use that information in planning their desired career. *Career exploration* is different from *career planning*, which focuses on thinking and planning about the future, where the forming is supported by the resources. The similarity from both is they focus on attitudes when handling works. Oftentimes, there are students who feel they do not need information about work assignments, or there are students who do not want to use resources such as parents for fear of authority figures, and there are also students who do not want to use resources such as acquaintances and teachers for fear that they will not be taken seriously, whereas a strong career exploration is a vital exploration to do before someone decides on a career choice. As with the scores of self-understand and career planning aspects, the scores of needs analysis of career exploration aspect are in the medium category. At the time of the pre-test, the score was still below 50% of the average. After the training is given, the results of the post-test score on this aspect were above 50%, meaning an increase in student understanding of what they must do to make career decisions, namely the knowledge of *career exploration*.

4.6 World of Work Information

The concept of *world of work information* has two basic components. First, is knowledge of the importance of accomplishing developmental tasks, as when students must explore their interests and abilities, how students learn about their work, and why others can switch jobs. Second, have a thorough knowledge of job assignments in a variety of job choices, as well as a behaviour expected of job applicants. It is important to have some knowledge about the world of work before making effective career decision. The operational definition of this training is the amount of information students have about majors and tertiary institutions, which is related to knowledge about their interests and abilities, information about the activities and lessons within the majors and tertiary institutions of interest, the environment surrounding the institution of interest, the requirements of enrolment in the higher education institution of interest, and what professions in line with the major taken by the student after graduating from the institution. The scores gained for this aspect are in the low category when needs analysis data was collected and remain low during the pre-test. The lack of student knowledge on the *world of work information* confused the students when planning and deciding for the right choice of career, Nevertheless, the scores increase after the training is given. The increasing student's understanding on the *world of work information* aspect ease them to make a career decision.

4.7 Decision Making

An idea of Super stated that students' ability to make a career decision is an important aspect in vocation maturity concept. This concept emphasizes in the ability to use knowledge and ideas to make career decisions. Asking students about how they plan for their career can help find out whether they have made a good career decision or not. Operational understanding in this training is that students use their knowledge and abilities in making career based on the knowledge of appropriate ways in making career decisions and rationality as well as the ability to estimate the consequences/risks of selected career decisions. This aspect is the link between the foundation of career decision and 3 components of career orientation process. This aspect gains low score both on needs analysis and pre-test results. Some students still find making career decision difficult. This is caused by the lack of knowledge and understanding of the components in making career decisions, namely self-understanding, *career planning*, *career exploration*, and *world of work information*. The results of the post-test score increased after the training was given. All 21 students participating in the study show significant increase in scores.

Overall, the measurement results from career maturity training are obtained from the total score of the *pre-test* and *post-test*. The Wilcoxon test analysis found that the results Asymp Sig (2-tailed) $0:00 < 0:05$, where the probability test result is of < 0.05 , it indicates that H_0 is accepted. We can conclude that the training is effective because there is an increase in *learning* effectiveness as measured with the *pre-test-treatment-post-test* method.

5. Recommendation

The suggestions we can give for the next researchers to make a detailed results from each of career maturity aspect and give an appropriate and profound intervention to an aspect with low score results.

While suggestions the researchers can offer too schools are more into providing knowledge and information about career decision making process through trainings, coachings, and individual or group counselling to students since they are at grade X, also giving the students of grade XII guidance through trainings, coaching's, and counselling when it is time for them to decide for a career after graduating from high school.

To students, we can support them to engage in activities suitable with their hobbies or interests, to know their potential and develop what they are good at better. Use social media to explore all the information needed with the next career decision (major, university, grade, etc.), consult with their teachers, seniors, and alumni about the information related to their career target, and ask for psychologist to conduct a psycho test and career consultation to determine for the right career.

6. Conclusion

After going through a series of procedures and analysis, it can be concluded that the Career Orientation Training for Students of Class XII Social Science 3 of SMA 10 Bogor is

classified as effective. The results are seen from the measurements and analysis using SPSS and Wilcoxon Test with the probability of 0.000. Because the probability is < 0.005 , then H_0 is rejected, or the *pre-test* and *post-test* values tend to be significantly different. In other words, the training is effective in increasing knowledge about the career orientation process for class XII Social Science 3 students at SMA 10 Bogor.

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